

ADVANCED TECHNOLOGIES AND INNOVATIVE METHODS FOR DEVELOPING THE FORESIGHT COMPETENCE OF FUTURE MANAGERS

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Abstract. *The article analyzes in detail the ways of developing the foresight competence of future managers based on advanced technologies and innovative teaching methods, and also shows modern methods of teaching core subjects, including Management, in the field of management education. The author's definition of pedagogical technology is indicated, a mental map of an improved methodology for teaching "Management" is developed. Based on the role of independent education in the development of foresight competence, it is recommended to use "Telecommunication educational projects" as digital technologies.*

Keywords: *competence, manager, foresight competence, pedagogical technology, innovation, method, methodology, mental card, digital technology.*

1. Introduction

In the current era of globalization, the search for innovative ways of training specialists is the most important and global trend for many universities in the world. Foresight in teaching (the use of foresight in education) is one of the modern world trends, and this direction is an advanced educational technology that requires the development of foresight research [1] in the system of school and university education.

The concept of advanced educational technologies was first introduced into science by the Russian philosopher Academician Arkady Dmitrievich Ursul, who considers advanced educational technologies to be a fundamental and constructively important idea in the strategy of increasing the intellectual potential of the nation. The concept of advanced educational technologies includes a principled approach to the future of a university graduate in a professional environment after graduation [2]. In the advanced education system, a certain part of the educational process is devoted to the study of new fundamental knowledge, processes and technologies. The main goal of Foresight Education, operating in the United States, is to promote and implement the foresight methodology in education around the world. The specialists of this organization organized educational courses, trainings and seminars on the methodology of foresight for teachers and students of geography, biology, linguistics, history, physics, chemistry in such countries as the Czech Republic, the USA, the Netherlands, China, Bulgaria and other Latvia. The authors and creators of the Foresight Education portal declared the importance of foresight education in the pedagogical process and noted the possibility of reaching a completely new level of quality in the education system. Through foresight, future specialists will have the competence to anticipate and predict the development of changes and uncertainties in the period of rapid development, the development of problems arising in non-standard situations, and to develop quick decisions on their solutions [3].

The choice and application of innovative pedagogical technologies in the training of future managers in specialized subjects, including "Management", taking into account the development of foresight competence, is based on the extreme complexity of innovative management. The main task of managers is to foresee the dynamics of the development of innovative processes, to choose the right strategy based on the analysis. Expansion of innovative management processes also requires improvement of training methods for future managers. In order for managers to know their new tasks in innovative policy, it is necessary to have personal qualities, that is, to know self-management. One of the distinctive features of training managers should be providing future managers with conceptual knowledge such as foresight and forecasting, the ability of correctly determine the goal, the formation of tasks and the determination of ways to solve them, and the development of active management. However, today's training methodology does not fully provide managers with the ability to solve these urgent issues.

The main goal of the science of "Management" is to provide students with innovative activity experiences, innovations, inventions management, the object and subjects of production team management, the fact that the leader is the main manager of the work team, the relations of employees in self-management in the management of work teams in the conditions of the market economy, financial stimulation of the innovations of the current era. , management of the innovative environment in the work team, deepening of the knowledge of the innovative management regarding the foreign experience, theoretical and practical study of the science and formation of solid knowledge and skills in this science. In addition, future managers need to integrate in new types of organizations and all-round development processes;

- development of a comprehensive development strategy of the company;
- systematic approach in innovation management; the essence of the concept of the life cycle of news;
- description of concepts and approaches in innovation management;
- organizational forms of innovative development, characteristics of future innovative organizations;
- selection and formation of an innovative strategy in the enterprise; new technologies of social management;
- mutual social cooperation of project groups;
- Strategic innovation marketing; defining innovation management strategy and tactics; innovative management innovative projects and efficiency evaluation methods;
- They should have theoretical knowledge and practical skills on comparative analytical indicators of investment and innovation projects efficiency.

2. Research methods

Methodology is derived from the Greek word "methodos" and is a ready-made "recipe", "algorithm", "order" or methods and ways of carrying out some purposeful activity [4,5,6]. The methodology is widely used in the teaching process of human activity [7,8] in the field of pedagogy and in other fields and industries. Methodology is different from the term method, a method is a way of doing specific tasks. For example, the mathematical treatment of experimental data can be considered as a method, while the selection of specific criteria or characteristics of research are known as a methodology.

The methodology of teaching management sciences, including "Management", can be understood as private didactics, theory of management education, experience and research that researches the laws of teaching management sciences.

Methodology is a pedagogical science based on general educational goals and tasks. The problem of creating a classification of teaching methods is one of the most important controversial issues of modern pedagogical didactics. Since the method is a universal category and "multidimensional education", it has many signs and criteria, and these are the basis for creating a classification. The natural differentiation and integration of knowledge about the teaching methodology reflects the fact that there are different approaches to creating its classification, and therefore a single and perfect classification has not been developed until now. Different authors used different bases and criteria in developing the classification of teaching methods [9].

In the course of this research, methods such as analysis of scientific and teaching-methodical literature, pedagogical observation, comparative analysis, generalization, mental maps, pedagogical experiment-test, and mathematical-statistical analysis were used.

3. Results

The application of innovative pedagogical technologies in the teaching of management science creates an innovative educational environment. The level of formation and development of foresight competence in future managers is primarily determined by the pedagogical technologies used in teaching specialist subjects. Pedagogical technology is a set of pedagogic-psychological methods and methods aimed at solving the issues of student education, upbringing, and personality development and implemented because of a certain sequence. Different scientists have defined pedagogical technology differently, but the content and essence have not changed. Pedagogical technology based on the analysis of definitions given by V.P.Bespalko, V.M.Monakhov, M.V.Klarin, I.Ya.Larner, B.M.Farberman, T.Sakomoto and Uzbek scientists N.Saidakhmatov, A.Ochilovs taking into account the requirements of the current innovative educational environment, we define: *"Pedagogical technology develops depending on the innovations in the technical support of the educational process, student thinking, socio-economic relations in society, state policy in the field of education, the information space of society ("Internet"), the possibilities of its use, the spiritual world of educators and learners, and the level of material support. , is an evolving innovative project"* (author's definition).

However, innovation and innovative pedagogical technology differ in content. Pedagogical innovation (innovation, innovation) is a goal-oriented change that effectively affects the development and operation of an educational institution by introducing elements of sustainable innovation. Innovative pedagogical technologies are a set of modern teaching methods and technical tools aimed at imparting knowledge to students (audiences) on a specific subject (subject) and forming their personality during the educational process.

E.M. Korotkova, A.P. Panfilova, E.M. The analysis of scientific research by scientists such as Trenenkova shows that improving the training of managers is one of the most urgent tasks [10].

Nowadays, along with the traditional (reproductive) technologies of teaching specialized subjects, including "Management", modular teaching, developmental education, step-by-step formation of mental movement, collective interaction, full mastery, teaching at different levels, adaptive teaching, programmed teaching, problem-based there are innovative pedagogical technologies such as teaching, development of creative activity, project method. [11] But they are rarely used in the training of future managers in higher education institutions of Uzbekistan [12].

The methodology of teaching management science is a science of the processes of teaching, education and development, which is explained by the specific features of this science. Studying and improving the methodology of teaching specialty subjects (management subjects) in the field of management education leads to the formation of a modern pedagogical outlook, reflexive-critical thinking and the formation of the teacher's professional competence in business education.

The main tasks of the management science teaching methodology include the formation of concepts about teaching methods and methods in higher education, the organization of student mastery processes, the use of modern pedagogical and digital technologies in higher education, the characteristics of traditional and distance learning, the development and improvement of professional self-development and assessment technology [13,14,15].

4. Discussion

The author defined the task of teaching management science methodology:

1. Determination of the role of specialty (management) subjects in the training of bachelors in the field of "Management" education.
2. Preparation, improvement and implementation of educational and working educational programs in science, electronic module educational-methodical and scientific-information complex of science.
3. Determining the content of the science modules and the mastering sequence.
4. Development of organizational forms, methods and methods of teaching students, taking into account the specific characteristics of science in the field of management.
5. Development and implementation of didactic support of the educational process.

Based on the analysis of the method of teaching the subject, the author developed a mental map of the methods of teaching the subject of management (see Figure 1). Mental cards are one of the innovative pedagogical technologies, which are rarely used in the higher education system of Uzbekistan.

Mental cards (mind mapping, mind mapping) are a convenient and effective visual way of expressing an opinion about events, processes, objects and new ideas. It can be used to organize new innovative ideas in a clear sequence, to record ideas in a small volume, to analyze and classify data, to organize decisions made on a problem. This method is not widely used compared to the traditional method, but it is accepted as the shortest and most understandable way to express the thought in writing [16].

In the teaching of management science, like other specialized subjects, the topic can be explained through visual, practical, oral and written methods. Of course, the highest effect is achieved when these methods are used in a complex manner. This teaching method differs from previously created methods in that it takes into account the use of electronic teaching resources [17] based on digital technologies in the educational process. For example, telecasts, slides (including multimedia and animated slides), computer programs, didactic computer games, various tests are included in the presentation style.

Figure 1. Mental map of improved methods of teaching management science

Also, in order to form and develop the independent and scientific-creative competences of students, debates and discussions are included in the oral style, and thesis (articles) writing, quotations, annotations, and reviews are included in the written style. Of course, these methods will be more effective if they are used in the organization of independent education. Today's traditional technology of independent education does not meet the requirements of the time, because today independent education in the credit-module system makes up 50-60% of the total study hours allocated for the subject, but it is carried out by preparing abstracts, summarizing the topic or completing other types of individual assignments. Organization of independent education based on digital technologies, in which the use of educational telecommunication projects is the most modern solution to this issue [18].

It should be noted that telecommunications training projects are not televised training. Educational telecommunication projects are organized on a computer basis through Internet networks, have a common problem, goal, agreed methods and methods of activity, and known as cooperative educational, research, creative, scientific and playful activities of students aimed at achieving a common result. The ideas based on the discussions are summarized, the initial strategic plan (roadmap) is corrected, supplemented, and presented, and a solution to the problem is determined. In the organization of independent education based on "Telecommunication educational projects", the teacher is the main coordinator, monitors, coordinates student activities, and evaluates them according to problem solving.

5. Conclusion

It is worth noting that in the development of future managers' foresight competence, the correct choice of advanced technologies and innovative methods of teaching specialized subjects, especially in the current era, the wide use of digital technologies, is of great importance. The application of innovative pedagogical technologies in the teaching of specialized subjects, including the subject of "Management", creates an innovative educational environment, and therefore the level of formation and development of foresight competence in future managers is

primarily determined by the correct choice of pedagogical technologies used in teaching specialized subjects.

REFERENCES

1. Rakhimova D.O. Methodology of formation of "Foresight competence" in future managers. // "Modern education" (Uzbekistan) magazine. 2022. - #3(112). B.68-74. (13.00.00. -#10)
2. Management of the application of technology for the purpose of determining future requirements and competences/Dmitry Sudakov, Pavel Luksha, Olga Strietska-Ilina, Gregg Conn, Christine Hoffman, Liana Khachatryan; Mejdunarodnoe Bureau is working. - Geneva: MOT, 2016. URL: <https://www.kazenergy.com/upload/document/atlas/p3.pdf>
3. Rakhimova D.O. Model formation forsayt-kompetentnosti u budushchikh menedzherov. //Magazine "Srednee professionalnoe obrazovanie (Russia)".2023 - No. 03. (13.00.00 - No. 21)
4. Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia. Methodology. URL: <https://ru.wikipedia.org> .
5. Methodology // Encyclopedic Dictionary of Brockhaus and Efron: in 86 volumes (82 volumes and 4 additional). - St. Petersburg. –P.1890-1907
6. Methodology // Small Encyclopedic Dictionary of Brockhaus and Efron: in 4 volumes - St. Petersburg. -P.1907-1909
7. Miropolsky S. I. "Methods of teaching literacy", St. Petersburg, 1876
8. Methodology of history // Encyclopedic Dictionary of Brockhaus and Efron: in 86 volumes (82 volumes and 4 additional). - St. Petersburg. -P.1890-1907
9. Babansky Yu.K. Classification of teaching methods. https://studbooks.net/1756455/pedagogika/klassifikatsiya_metodov_obucheniya_babanskiy.
10. Petrovskaya E.N. Methodology for training future managers in intra-company personnel development. Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of candidate of pedagogical sciences. Russian State Pedagogical University named after A.I. Herzen. 2007. URL:<http://www.dslib.net/teoria-vospitania/metodika-obuchenija-buduvih-menedzherov-vnutrifirmennomu-razvitiju-personala.html>.
11. Rakhimov O. D. Innovation pedagogical technology: project method as a technology that increases the quality of education //Karshi, TATU Karshi branches.
12. Raximov O. D. et al. Modern educational technologies //Tashkent," Science and Technology" Publishing House. – 2013.
13. Zinnurov U.G. Strategic marketing planning i upravlenie na predpriyatii: Ucheb. posobie. – Ufa: MAI, 2004
14. Kovalev A.I. Quality management. Many in few words. - M .: Standards and quality, 2007
15. Skok G.B. How to analyze your own pedagogical activity. - M .: Pedagogical Society of Russia, 2001.
16. Rakhimov O.D., Khudoykulov A.B. Innovative pedagogical technologies in higher education: mental-intellect-mind (mind-maps-mindmapping) cards.//QarMII, "Intellect" publishing house, 2021. -40p.
17. Rakhimov O. Requirements and technology for creating electronic educational resources //Sovremennoe obrazovanie (Uzbekistan). 2016. No. 2. - S. 45-50.
18. Rakhimov O. D. Requirements and technology for creating electronic educational resources //Sovremennoe obrazovanie (Uzbekistan). 2016. No. 2. - P. 45-50.